

YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA AMALGA OSHIRILAYOTGAN ISLOHOTLAR UCHINCHI RENESSANS POYDEVORI

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Annotatsiya. Mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning barchasi unda yashayotgan fuqarolarning tinch-totuvligi va yoshlarning zamonaviy bilimlar egallashi, xalq farovonligi, yurt tinchligini o'zida mujassam etgan bo'lib, yakdil bir g'oya "Milliy tiklanishdan milliy yuksalish g'oyasi" asosida amalga oshirib kelinyapti.

Kalit so'zlar: Strategiya, taraqqiyot, ma'rifat, islohot, renessans, jamiyat, siyosat, ma'naviyat, istiqbol.

THE REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN NEW UZBEKISTAN ARE THE FOUNDATION OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE

Abstract. All the reforms implemented in our country embody the peaceful harmony of the citizens living in it, the acquisition of modern knowledge by the youth, the well-being of the people, and the peace of the country. getting married

Key words: Strategy, development, enlightenment, reform, renaissance, society, politics, spirituality, perspective.

РЕФОРМЫ, РЕАЛИЗУЕМЫЕ В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ, ЯВЛЯЮТСЯ ОСНОВОЙ ТРЕТЬЕГО РЕНЕССАНСА.

Аннотация. Все реформы, реализуемые в нашей стране, воплощают мирное согласие проживающих в ней граждан, приобретение молодежью современных знаний, благополучие народа, мир вступающей в брак.

Ключевые слова: Стратегия, развитие, просвещение, реформа, ренессанс, общество, политика, духовность, перспектива.

Bugun "Harakatlar strategiyasidan – Taraqqiyot strategiyasi sari" ildamlab borar ekanmiz, u mamlakatimiz iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy taraqqiyoti, madaniy va ma'naviy yangilanishi uchun keng istiqbollari yo'lini ochib bermoqda. Yurtimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar tufayli jamiyatimiz iqtisodiy va ma'naviy-ma'rifiy yuksalish sari ildam qadam bosmoqda. Bugun jamiyatimiz hayotida ma'naviyat va ma'rifati rivojlantirish davlat siyosatining eng ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida e'tirof etilib, ma'naviy yangilanishlar mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar strategiyasida samarali natijalarga erishishimizga xizmat qilib kelmoqda.

Bu islohotlar strategiyasining dolzarbligi haqida davlatimiz rahbari Shavkat Mirziyoyev ta'kidlab o'tganlaridek: "Jamiyatimizning ma'naviy asoslarini mustahkamlash, madaniyat sohasini rivojlantirish, ilmiy-ijodiy tashkilotlar, muhtaram ziyolilarimiz faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash ham biz uchun ustuvor yo'nalishlardan biri bo'ladi"[1] -deb ta'kidlab o'tganlar.

Uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishda ma'naviyat va ma'naviy yangilanishlar masalasi O'zbekiston uchun doimo dolzarbligi inobatga olinib, uni umumdavlat darajasida hal qilishga katta e'tibor qaratib kelinmoqda. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, O'zbekistonda ma'naviyatga

oid davlat siyosati izchillik bilan hayotga tadbiiq etilmoqda va bu ishlarni quyda bosqichma-bosqich ko'rib chiqamiz.

Birinchidan, mamlakatimizda demokratik tamoyillarga asoslangan fuqarolik jamiyatini qurish maqsadida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish, modernizatsiya jarayonlarini izchil davom ettirish va ularning muvaffaqiyatli kechishini ta'minlash jamiyatning barcha a'zolari bilimi, dunyoqarashi, tajribasi va yangicha fikr yurita olishi - ma'naviyat va ma'naviy yangilanishlar bilan bog'liq ekanligi;

Ikkinchidan, jamiyatni yangilashda umuminsoniy ma'naviy qadriyatlar – adolat, halollik, tenglik, ahil qo'shnichilik va insonparvarlik kabi qadriyatlarni asrash, ularga yangicha mazmun bag'ishlab, yurtimizda tinchlik va demokratiya, farovonlik, vijdon erkinligi va har bir kishini kamol toptirish;

Uchinchidan, jamiyatimizda ro'y berayotgan demokratik va ma'naviy yangilanishlar tayyorlanayotgan kadrlar tafakkuri tarzida kuchli rivojlanishning yuzaga kelishi, xalq ruhiyatida kelajak hayotdagi farovonlikka ishonch paydo qilishi;

To'rtinchidan, tarixiy xotirani tiklash, milliy ma'naviy negizlarga tayanish, ozod shaxs, erkin fuqaro madaniyatini shakllantirishning to'liq mazmun-mohiyatini o'rganish, unga oid chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish, undan o'sib kelayotgan barkamol avlodni voyaga yetkazishda foydalanish, unga bog'liq ma'naviy-madaniy masalalarni o'rganish;

Beshinchidan, jamiyatimiz taraqqiyotida ma'naviy yangilanishimizning natijalari olim, mutaxassis, ijodkor va ziyolilar tomonlaridan tadqiqot ishlari olib borilishi, bu masalalarni to'liq sharhlash, unga oid kitob chop etilishi uchun shart-sharoitni yaratish dolzarb masala hisoblanadi.

Yangi O'zbekistondagi do'stlik va hamjihatlik muhiti – yurtimizda tinchlik va barqarorlikni ta'minlashga, strategik islohotlar samaradorligini oshirish hamda uning xalqaro maydondagi nufuzini yanada yuksaltirishga xizmat qiladi va mamlakatda amalga oshirilayotgan barcha islohotlar yakdil bir g'oya "Milliy tiklanishdan milliy yuksalish g'oyasi"[2] negizida umumlashgani va Yangi Oz'bekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar uchinchi renesans poydevori bo'lib xizmat qilishi tahsinga sazovor hisoblanadi. Bu kabi keng ko'lamli ishlarni amalga oshirishda mamlakatimizning milliy ma'naviyatini rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratilishi, birinchi navbatda, har bir insonning haqiqiy erkinligini ta'minlashga qaratilganligidir. Zero, o'zligini anglamagan odam, unga qancha imkon va sharoit yaratib bermang, voqean hur va ozod bo'la olmaydi.

Fikrimizcha, mustaqillik tufayli bir tizimdan ikkinchi tizimga o'tish davrida o'zlikni anglashning o'ziga xos ko'rinishlarini anglamasdan ma'naviy yuksalish va taraqqiyot darajasini anglab bo'lmaydi. Yuksak rivojlangan jamiyat esa o'zligini anglagan shaxslardan tarkib topishi mumkin. O'zligini anglagan yoki anglay boshlagan kishigina shaxs darajasiga ko'tariladi. Demak, o'zlikni anglash, avvalo, har bir insonning shaxsi, alohida "meni" bilan bog'liq. Suqrot ta'kidlaganidek, "O'zini anglagan inson o'zi uchun nima foydali va nimalarga qodir ekanligini yaxshi tushunadi. U qo'lidan keladigan ish bilan shug'ullanish asnosida o'z ehtiyojini qondiradi va saodatga erishadi. Har qanday xato va baxtsizliklardan xoli bo'ladi. Buning natijasi o'laroq, u o'zga odamlarni qadrlay oladi va ulardan ezgulik yo'lida foydalana oladi. Oqibatda o'zini kulfatlardan asraydi"[3].

Xulosa o'rnida shuni takidlash joizki, millat taraqqiyoti jarayonida iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy-siyosiy sohalarida yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal qilishda milliy o'z-o'zini anglash omili millatni jipslashtiradi va uni umum maqsadlar yo'lida harakatga keltiradi. U har qanday millat uchun yetakchi belgi hisoblanadi. U o'zining yaratuvchilik salohiyati bilan millatning asosiy belgilari tizimida yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi. Milliy o'z-o'zini anglash millatning abadiyligini ta'minlaydigan eng muhim omildir. Bu salohiyat millatning o'ziga xosligini va manfaatlarini himoya qilishga xizmat qiladi.

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